

Knowledge About The Mental Health and Mental Illness Among Adolescents

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Abstract

Background: People who fail to fulfill their roles and carryout responsibilities or whose behavior is inappropriate to the situation are viewed as Mental Illnesses. About 450 million people suffer from mental of behavioural disorders worldwide today, it was said that mental health problems are more common in developed world than developing world.

Aim: This study was aimed to assess the knowledge about mental health and mental illness among Adolescents population.

Methodology: A Quantitative Descriptive research design was used. 30 Adolescents were selected by using Purposive sampling technique who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and who were available during the period of data collection at selected Lawspetarea, Puducherry. Data was collected by using Self Structured Questionnaire.

Results: It represents the Level of Knowledge among 14(46.7%) of them comes under Moderate Knowledge, 10 (33.3%) of them comes under Adequate Knowledge and 6(20%) of them comes under Inadequate Knowledge.

Conclusion: The study conducted among 30 Adolescents. It reveals the significant with demographic variables such as staying in status at the level of knowledge. Majority of Adolescents have moderate knowledge. We provide opportunities for adolescents to gain knowledge regarding mental health and mental illness.

Key words: Knowledge, Adolescents, Mental Health, Mental Illness.

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Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, and not merely absence of disease or infirmity. "Mental health is defined as a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her

own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community"[1].

Mental health is a positive state in which one is responsible for self-awareness, self-directive, reasonable worry free and can cope with usual daily

tensions. Such individual's functions well in society are accepted within a group and are generally satisfied with their lives [2]. Components of mental health includes the ability to accept self. A mentally healthy individual feels comfortable about himself, the capacity to feel right towards others. An individual who enjoys good mental health is able to be sincerely interested in others welfare, the ability to fulfill life tasks. A mentally healthy person is able to think for himself, set reasonable goals and take his own decision[3].

Criteria for mental health person is adequate contact with reality, control of thoughts and imagination, efficiency in work and play, social acceptance, positive self concept and healthy emotional life.[3]

Indicators of mental health is the person with a positive attitude towards knowledge to accept the strength and limitations, growth, development and the ability for self actualization. [3]

Characteristics of mentally healthy person an individual an ability to make adjustments, the person as sense of personal worth and feels worth while and important, the individual solves his problem largely by his own effort and makes his own decision, person has a sense of responsibility, individual can give and accept love. The healthy people lives in a world of reality rather than fantasy. Individual has a variety of interests and generally lives a well balanced life of work, rest and recreation.[4]

Mental illness affects one in four peoples in the world by world health report. There is still no cure because of stigma. Thus mental health problem constitute one of the mental health problem in community. These were a general belief that clients with mental health problem were potentially dangerous.[5]

Mental disorders have been found to be relatively common, with more than one in three people in most countries. A WHO global survey indicates that anxiety disorders are the most common in all country, followed by mood disorders in all countries, while substance disorders and impulse control disorders were consistently less prevalent.[6]

Mental illness are very common, one fifth of American are suffer from mental disorder in a year and one fifth of school age children are also affected by these diseases. Mental illness may be manifested in various ways such as in effective problems solving, poor reality testing and impaired cognitive functioning[7]

Worldwide, 450 million people are suffering from mental illness and around 80% of them live in middle- and low-income countries.[8] One-third of the global burden of mental, neurological, and substance-use disorders is contributed by India and China.[9]

Materials and methods

A Quantitative Descriptive research design was used. 30 Adolescents were selected by using Purposive sampling technique who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and who were available during the period of data collection at selected Lawspet area, Puducherry. Data was collected by using Self Structured Questionnaire.

The tools used for data collection were divided into two sections. Section A includes demographic variables and section B comprised of Self Structured Questionnaire consists of 20 questions scored individually from 14 to 20. A total score of 20 is an adequate knowledge in mental health and mental illness, a score of 7-13 indicates moderate knowledge and whilst a score between 1 and 6 is an indicate of inadequate knowledge of mental health and mental illness.

The data was collected after obtaining permission from the concerned authority. Informed consent was obtained from the each Adolescents population prior to data collection. The data was collected by using Self Structured Questionnaire schedule to all adolescents population who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and available at the time of data collection in the Lawspet area.

Data analysis

Plan for data analysis were done using Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16.0 software for Windows. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the frequencies, percentage and mean

Results

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of all participants involved in this study. Majority of Adolescents 16 (53.3%) belonged to the age group of 14 – 16 years, 24(80%) Females were comes under Gender, 17 (56.7%) Hindu were comes under Religion, 17 (56.7%) adolescents were educated up to 9th – 10th, 15 (50%) adolescents father's occupational status were government employed and 18 (60%) adolescents had a family income of more than Rs.10000.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the Study Subjects**N = 30**

S. No	Demographic variables	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age group		
	10 to 13 Years	9	30%
	14 to 16 Years	16	53.3%
	17 to 19 Years	5	16.7%
2.	Gender		
	Male	6	20%
	Female	24	80%
3.	Religion		
	Hindu	17	56.7%
	Christian	6	20%
	Muslim	7	23.3%
4.	Education		
	6 th to 8 th	05	16.7%
	9 th – 10 th	17	56.7%
	11 th – 12 th	08	26.6%
5.	Father Occupational status		
	Private sector	6	20%
	Government sector	15	50%
	Self employment	7	23.3%
	Unemployment	2	6.7%
6.	Family Income		
	Below Rs. 4000/ month	NIL	NIL
	Rs. 4000 – 6000/ month	1	3.3%
	Rs. 6000 – 10,000/month	11	36.7%
	Above Rs. 10,000/month	18	60%

Table 2: Distribution of subjects based on Area of Residence**N=30**

Area of Residence	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE %
RURAL	16	53.3%
URBAN	14	46.7%

The above table 2 describes the distribution of subjects based on Area of Residence. Majority 16 (53.3%) of them were belongs to Rural area and 14 (46.7%) of them were belongs to Urban area.

Table 3: Distribution of subjects based on Family history of any Mental Illness:**N=30**

Family history of Mental Illness	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	17	56.7%
No	13	43.3%

The above table 3 describes the distribution of subjects based on Family history of Mental Illness. Majority 17 (56.7%) of them were in Yes and 13 (43.3%) of them were in No.

Table 4.: Distribution of subjects based on Do you have any Knowledge on Mental Health**N=30**

Do you have any Knowledge on Mental Health	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE
YES	15	50%
NO	15	50%

The above table 4 describes the distribution of subjects based on Do you have any Knowledge on Mental Health. They have equally in 15(50%) of them were in Yes and 15 (50%) of them were in No.

TABLE 5: Frequency and Percentage wise distribution for Level of Knowledge: N=30

S.NO	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE %
1.	Inadequate Knowledge	6	20%
2.	Moderate Knowledge	14	46.7%
3.	Adequate Knowledge	10	33.3%

The above table 5 describes the frequency and percentage wise distribution for Level of Knowledge among 14(46.7%) of them comes under Moderate Knowledge, 10 (33.3%) of them comes under Adequate Knowledge and 6(20%) of them comes under Inadequate Knowledge.

Fig 1: Frequency and Percentage Wise Distribution for Level of Knowledge.

Discussion

The result of the present study showed that the level of knowledge among adolescents in moderate knowledge among them 14 (46.7).

The present study was supported by the study conducted by DR. P C SEN, A study on knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding mental health illnesses in Amdanga block, West Bengal. The results shows that SEM identified well-define domains in the attitude part. 94.9% says that they are willing to live with a people with mental illness. 14.9% has actually done so. 10]

The present study was supported by the study conducted by C Ruth Sneha, Mohan M Reddy(2019) Awareness and attitude toward mental illness among a rural population in Kolar. About 22% thought that people with mental health problems are largely to blame for their own condition and one-third felt that someone with a mental illness was usually dangerous. The study also identified the magnitude of the stigma attached to mental illness.[11]

The present study was supported by the study conducted by Eyasu H. Tesfamariam (2018), Attitude towards Mental Illness among Secondary School Students in Asmara, Eritrea: A Cross-Sectional Study.

The results shows that The majority (97.01%) of students had no family history of mental illness, and 28.8% of them had a neighbor with a history of mental illness.[12]

The present study was supported by the study conducted by Mr. Praveen L Subravgoudar (2019) A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge regarding Mental Illness among Rural Adults in selected Area, at Kolhapur. The knowledge of mental illness among adults was found 70% good knowledge, average knowledge among 16% adults, very good knowledge among 14% adults and no one with poor knowledge. [13].

Conclusion

The study conducted among 30 Adolescents. It reveals the significant with demographic variables such as staying in status at the level of knowledge. Majority of Adolescents have moderate knowledge. We provide opportunities for adolescents to gain knowledge regarding mental health and mental illness.

Recommendations

Based on findings of the present study the following recommendation have been made:

- Similar study can be conducted in large sample

- The sample study can be conducted in different settings
- The study can be implemented that the various states of India.

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